

How Satisfied are Today's Women?

Meenakshi Chaturvedi¹ and Poonam Mishra²

1. Assistant Professor, Dept. of Teacher Education, IES University, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh.
2. Associate Professor, Dept. of Teacher Education, D.A.V(P.G) College, Dehradun, Uttarakhand

Received : 20/07/2022

1st BPR : 30/07/2022

2nd BPR : 13/08/2022

Accepted : 21/08/2022

Abstract

Women, from time immemorial were supposed to be the epicenter of love, affection and care of the children. Perhaps the joy which is at the root of all activities is supplied from home but are today's women really happy with their life in the present modern Indian society? The present study has tried to find out the answer to the same question. The data were collected on 295 working and 296 non-working women of Dehradun district. Srivastava and Allam's Life Satisfaction Scale was utilized for assessing the life satisfaction of both working and non-working women. The result of the present study has revealed that, life satisfaction of both working and non-working women were average however, mean scores revealed that working women experienced slightly higher life satisfaction in comparison to non-working women.

Keywords: Life Satisfaction (LS), Life Satisfaction - Dimensions (LS - Dim), Working women (WW), Non-working women (NWW)

Introduction

A woman is the fountain head of home and all familial activities revolve around her. With the untiring efforts of a woman, the place which is built out of bricks breathes in a real sense where all family members cherish their dreams and live their life to the brim of satisfaction. When a woman chooses to remain at home and perform housework i.e. as a pure homemaker, she administers a variety of household work. As a dutiful mother she stays by the side of her children when they need her and as a faithful wife she brings joy, solace and inspiration to her husband and other family members. When a woman joins the workforce her role in present date goes much beyond the home and the bringing up of children. Equipped with her new role, she is now sharing equal responsibilities with the man for the development of home as well as society in all its aspects. Now the question arises - is she really happy and satisfied in exhibiting her perspective role as a homemaker (in case of non-working woman) or as a working lady (in case of working woman).

In this era of competitive world, in the wake of proving oneself, there has become a neck to neck competition in almost even sphere of life. Working as well as non-working women faces tough challenges in process of meeting their needs-for instance, need for identity, need for exposure, need for money etc. This ever-increasing need brings a state of dejection or anxiety. A state of imbalance arises when these needs remain unfulfilled. Depression, positive emotions and cheerfulness are personality traits that most influence life satisfaction (Upmanyu, 1991; Schimmack, 2004). (Feather & O' Brien, 1986) reported that non-working led to decrease in perceived competencies, activity and life satisfaction and increase in depressive effect. Studying the psychological effects of unemployment (Eisenberg and Lazarsfeld, 1938) found that unemployment deteriorates the self-confidence and independence. Thus, life satisfaction is an important index and is the most important, pious and effective predictor of the extent to which a married woman is successful in her life, therefore, above discussion paved the path to explore the life satisfaction of educated, married working and non-working women.

Objective

To study the life satisfaction of working and non-working women.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the life satisfaction of working and non-working women.

Method

Sample

Keeping in mind the nature of present study, Normative Survey Method was found to be most suitable for this study and hence it was employed. The population for the present study is a finite & existent one comprising of married, educated, working & non-working women of Dehradun district. 295 working and 296 non-working, educated (minimum till graduation level) and married women were selected by Random Purposive Sampling technique. Working women comprised of teachers, bankers, scientists, women working in State and Central Govt. offices etc. likewise non-working women comprised of full-time home makers as well as socially active women who had a feeling to serve the mankind without being influenced by any kind of favour or remuneration.

Tool Used

Life Satisfaction Scale – By Dr. Q. G. Allam and Dr. Ramji Srivastava

Administration of Tool

The researcher visited personally and contacted directly to the subjects (i.e., working and non-working women) of the present study. Age group of women were between 22 to 55 years. The selected subjects were contacted according to their convenience at their residences or offices. Random selection of the total sample was done and they were provided with duly pre-tested tool. All the instructions were given clearly and confusions were clarified. All the respondents were assured of confidentiality of their responses and were requested to fill the questionnaire without skipping any statement. The filled forms were collected, there and then, for further investigation.

Statistical Treatment

To study the life satisfaction of working and non-working women t-test was applied on six dimensions of life satisfaction i.e., Health, Personal, Economy, Marital, Social, Job and likewise Total life satisfaction was studied and obtained data was tabulated as shown in table - 1. Levels of life satisfaction was determined through the obtained mean score, like low level of life satisfaction, average level of life satisfaction or high level of life satisfaction and women were categorised accordingly.

A Study of Life Satisfaction of Working and Non-Working Women

- (i) Comparison between working women (WW) and non-working women (NWW) on the grounds of Life Satisfaction (LS)

Table-01: Significance of Difference between WW and NWW on the grounds of LS

LS Dimension(s)	WW N=295		NWW N=296		T
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
Health(H)	5.6475	1.56637	6.1993	1.46512	4.423**
Personal(P)	6.8881	1.39643	7.0878	1.34002	1.774
Economy(E)	6.7322	1.57342	6.4291	1.68594	2.260*
Marital(M)	8.4814	1.27462	7.9426	1.21016	5.270**
Social(S)	8.8000	1.03543	8.8682	1.06064	0.791
Job(J)	7.8508	1.38927	7.6051	1.67579	1.941
Total – LS	44.4000	4.18484	44.1321	4.67538	0.734

LS Score < 30 = Low* LS; LSS 30 - 45 = Average** LS; LSS > 45 = High*** LS
(Max. score for each dimension H, P, E, M, S, J = 10)

Result And Discussion

The findings on life satisfaction as discussed in Table-1 are summarized below on six grounds.

1. Health (H)

The working women (WW) and non-working women (NWW) when compared on the dimension Health ($t = 4.423$, $p = 0.01$) yielded significant variations. The maximum score for H is 10. When mean scores were examined, it was revealed that, in comparison to WW, NWW's health was better. It might be due to the fact that, NWW get ample time to look after their health and can be involved in various health care measures on the other hand WW bear dual responsibilities, managing lots of stress at their work place and as well as home so it might be possible that their health is overlooked in some cases. Jain and Gunthey (2001) obtained similar findings. Sharma et.al., (2001) assessed the impact of job stress on the mental health of women. The sample comprised 120 full-time working, part-time working, and non-working women. The moderate job stress group was comparatively free from symptoms of mental disorders as compared to the high job stress group. The high as well as low job stress groups reported higher psychological distress than the moderate job stress group.

2. Personal (P)

Insignificant differences were reported in comparing working and non-working women on personal aspect of LS. The obtained result depicts a picture that both the groups of women perceived themselves as more satisfied from their personal point of view. It might be because of the fact that, both the groups of women were equally satisfied from their lives. In case of NWW they were satisfied in successfully managing their house, giving fruitful lessons to their children, providing a helping hand in their husband's work thus they gain personal satisfaction in fulfilling their familial roles, whereas in case of WW, their economic status raises their self-concept (Sujata, 1990) and requisite confidence and strength to fulfil their dual responsibilities which gives them personal satisfaction.

3. Economy (E)

The working women (WW) and non-working women (NWW) when compared on the dimension Economy ($t = 2.260$, $p = 0.05$) yielded significant variations. Statistical analysis reveals that, WW were comparatively more economically sound than their NWW counterparts. Perhaps, the figure reflects the true picture of economic empowerment of women. When a woman is professionally strong, she feels strength in her and definitely, a satisfaction from her status in the society. Congruent findings were reported from Aggarwal (1987) and Anandh RajKumar (1995).

4. Marital (M)

The working women (WW) and non-working women (NWW) when compared on the dimension Marital ($t = 5.270$, $p = 0.01$) yielded significant variations. The obtained result depicts a picture that, both the groups of women WW and NWW perceived themselves to be very highly satisfied on grounds of marital satisfaction however, statistical analysis reveals that, WW perceived more marital satisfaction (9 out of max. Life Satisfaction Score for Marital dimension, i.e., 10) than their NWW counterparts. In a study conducted on "marital adjustment and life satisfaction among dual career couples" consistent findings were reported by Gupta and Joshi (2009). Perhaps, it is an outcome of understanding and compatibility between the couples which adds to the marital satisfaction in working class women. Today husbands willingly provide a helping hand to his professional wife, be it any household activity or purchasing for house hold items or any recreational activity like freaking out on weekends. As a result of this marital bonding is strengthened between the spouses and they experience high marital satisfaction. Consistent findings were reported by (Juyal and Gaur, 2007). They reported that happiness of husband and wife, ability to deal satisfactorily with disagreement, togetherness and good financial adjustment are the most important criteria of successfull married life. Similarly, Aminabhav & Kulkarni (2000) in a study on Marital Adjustment of 50 working women and 50 housewives (23-55 yrs) found that working women had significantly higher marital satisfaction than housewives.

5. Social (S):

WW and NWW reported to have insignificant differences between them on social aspect of their life satisfaction. The obtained result depicts a picture that both the groups of women perceived themselves to be very highly satisfied in respect to social point of view. It might be due to the fact that, NWW due to sufficient time can manage meeting the relatives, attending to several social functions and so on. Similarly, WW especially teacher due to their less working hours can manage to handle their social relationships to a better degree. Also, due to impact of teaching profession a teacher is in direct contact of her students, their parents, and other family members and relatives. So these WW were influenced with a strong social network, which was reflected in their satisfied social life.

6. Job (J):

A very interesting result was obtained when comparisons were made on this aspect of life satisfaction. Insignificant differences were reported between WW and NWW in respect to Job aspect of life satisfaction. The obtained result depicts a picture that, both the groups of women perceived themselves to be highly satisfied in respect to job point of view. This shows that NWW considered home management as their job so they considered themselves to be home makers rather than house wife. According to them housekeeping activity is a full-time job and they enjoyed their status of being a housewife

7. Overall life satisfaction (LS):

When WW and NWW were compared in respect to overall LS insignificant variations were reported. Both the groups of women perceived themselves to be average** (LSS range between 30 to 45) satisfied from their life. Similarly, Jan and Massod (2008) concluded that women of all age groups possess average life satisfaction. Sultania, Thakur and Prabhanshu (2010) indicated no difference between working women and non-working women on total adjustment scores, on Home adjustment scores, on health adjustment scores on social adjustment scores and even on emotional adjustment scores. Results obtained in their study revealed that, in modern age non-working women are also educated so they are equally efficient and capable like working women.

Conclusion

Findings of the study conclude that, when working women and non-working women were compared in respect to overall Life Satisfaction ($t = 0.734$, n.s.) insignificant differences were reported which means that both the groups of women considered themselves as having average level of life satisfaction (mean score ranged between 30 to 45) and we cannot say that one group is having higher life satisfaction than the other group. However, when they were compared on different parameters of life satisfaction, data reveal that WW significantly differed from their NWW counterparts on the dimensions of Health ($t = 4.423$, $p = 0.01$), Economy ($t = 2.260$, $p = 0.05$) and Marital ($t = 5.270$, $p = 0.01$). Mean scores show that, WW scored higher on economy ($M=6.7322$) and marital ($M=8.4814$) dimensions of LS in comparison to NWW on the contrary, NWW reported to be highly satisfied from health ($M= 6.1993$) point of view as compared to their WW counterparts ($M=5.6475$). Therefore, a significant difference existed between WW and NWW on the dimensions- Health, Economy and Marital but the rest of the dimensions of this scale i.e., Personal, Social and Job had not shown any remarkable difference between both the groups of women.

Suggestions

1. Women should be assured of their security outside their home. For this a convenient pick and drop facility should be provided by the organization in which they work.
2. Organization should have an eye on personal as well as professional growth of their employees. This will act as a reinforcement to pursue their job with satisfaction.
3. Self-concept enhancement programmes should be organized from time to time to boost the self-image and potentials of both teaching professionals and other professionals which will ultimately lead to their life satisfaction.

4. Therapy and remedial sessions should be organized for non-working women to discuss their problems relating to mental and physical health.
5. Socializing sector should counsel the husband and other family members of non-working women to support their women in the daily household chores.
6. Family members should give respect to the unending efforts of their women in managing their house.
7. Some free time should be provided to non-working women to relax and take a pause while their household activities.
8. The money saved by these women out of their house expenses should be given to them to be spent at their own will. This will render positive outcomes in a non-working women's life as it will provide economic independence with which their life satisfaction will increase and they will consider themselves no less worth than working women.
9. Women must be given opportunity in decision making behaviour.
10. Political empowerment of women must be allowed to continue.
11. Holistic approach for women's development in different fields like home, social, economic, legal, political and cultural must be given importance to enhance women's status in society.
12. National policies relating to women in the field of health, education, nutrition, family, outlook, employment, social status. etc. must be reviewed and revised with greater emphasis upon women and must be implemented in true sense.

References

- Agarwal, K. (1987). A study of the effect of parental encouragement upon educational development of the students. D. phil. Thesis in Education, Garhwal University.
- Aminabhav, Vijaylaxmi A. & Kulkarni, Vidya, R. (2000). (Karnatak U. Dept. of Psycho., Dharwad). Marital Adjustment of working women and housewives. *Journal of Projective Psycho and Mental Health*, 7(2), 153-158.
- Anandharajkumar, P. (1995). Multiprogramme approach to women's economic independence, *Kurukshetra*, Vol. XLIII, No. 11, 73-76.
- Gupta, Neeta. and Joshi, Renuka. (2009). Marital adjustment and life satisfaction among dual career couples. *Psycho - linguistics Association of India*, 39(1), 45-48.
- Jan, Muzamil and Masood, Tasia (2008). An assessment of life satisfaction among women. *Extension and communication Institute of home Science, University of Kashmir*.
- Jain, Neeta, & Gunthey, Ravi. (2001). (JNV U. Jodhpur). Dual role and mental health among working women. *Journal of Community Guidance and Research*, 18(2), 183-187.
- Upmanyu, Kalpana. (1991). A study of marital adjustment of working and non-working women in relation to certain socio psychological variables. Ph.D., Psy. Mohanlal Sukhadia Univ.
- Hota, Sujata (1990). Working women's perception of their self and environment in relation to job and life satisfaction. Ph. D. Education. Kurukshetra University.

